

Intensifying Sports in the Curriculum: Perspectives of the School Coordinators

Gilleville C. Ricaborda

Abstract. This study unearthed the experiences of school coordinators in intensifying sports in the curriculum. There were ten (10) teachers of Sta. Cruz North District, Division of Davao Del Sur, who participated in the study. This study used a phenomenological approach to extract the participants' ideas. An in-depth interview was conducted to gather information regarding their experiences and coping mechanisms. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged: the experiences of school coordinators focused on the challenges with the resources and balancing academic and athletic priorities. And increased student engagement. The identified coping mechanisms for the challenges delved into advocacy and communication, professional development, and community partnership. The education management insights drawn from the study's findings underscored the importance of a holistic approach, resource management strategies, and a student-centered approach. Results revealed that intensifying sports in the curriculum was crucial to the learning landscape. Moreover, sports promote comprehensive student development and create meaningful impact on learner experiences.

KEY WORDS

1. student engagement 2. advocacy 3. communication

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1. Introduction

Sports, with their transformative power, have long been recognized as a potent tool for fostering physical health, teamwork, and discipline in students. Beyond the arena, sports offer a unique opportunity to instill life skills, values, and character traits that extend far beyond the playing field. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the vital role that sports play in holistic education, and this paradigm shift has led to the integration of sports into the curriculum of schools worldwide. This transformation, with its inspiring potential, has not only enriched the educational experience but has also opened doors to a multitude of benefits for students. From the perspective of school coordinators and individuals at the forefront of shaping educational policies and experiences, including sports in the curriculum is a strategic decision with profound implications. This shift represents a holistic approach to education that values academic success, personal growth, physical well-being, and character development. School coordinators are instrumental in charting this course, ensuring that sports become integral to the educational journey. From the global perspective as Erin,., Russel (2012). In Canada, as in many countries, integrating sports into the school curriculum has challenges and issues.

One of the primary challenges is the allocation of resources. School budgets are often stretched, and there is competition for resources between academic programs and sports initiatives. Coordinators must navigate the financial constraints to ensure that sports programs are adequately supported. Ensuring that sports programs are inclusive and accessible to all students is a priority. Issues related to equity and inclusivity can arise, such as providing opportunities for students with disabilities or those from diverse socio-economic backgrounds. To deliver effective sports programs, schools need qualified coaches and instructors. Recruiting, training, and retaining qualified sports staff can be challenging, especially in remote or underserved areas. Coordinators must work to seamlessly integrate sports into the curriculum without disrupting academic schedules. This requires careful planning and coordination with teachers and academic departments. Many schools face challenges regarding the availability and condition of sports facilities and equipment. Upgrading or maintaining facilities can be costly, and access to appropriate sports equipment is essential for safe and effective programs. Encouraging all students to participate in sports actively can be a challenge. Coordinators must find ways to engage students who may not be naturally inclined toward sports or may have had negative experiences. Ensuring the safety and health of students during sports activities is paramount. Coordinators must address injury prevention, concussion protocols, and overall well-being issues. In the Philippines, intensifying sports into the school curriculum is complex, presenting opportunities and challenges. As we explore this initiative's issues, it is essential to adopt an informative and balanced essay tone, highlighting the nuances and potential solutions within the context of the Philippines' educational landscape. Integrating sports into the school curriculum is a multifaceted task that school coordinators in the Philippines must navigate. While this initiative holds significant promise for the holistic development of students, several pressing issues need to be addressed. One of the primary issues that school coordinators face in the Philippines is the allocation of resources. With limited budgets, schools often need help to provide adequate sports facilities, equipment, and qualified coaches. Finding ways to secure additional funding and resources is essential to ensure the success of sports programs. In a diverse country like the Philippines, ensuring equitable access to sports programs is paramount. Coordinators must address issues related to inclusivity, accommodating students with varying abilities, backgrounds, and interests. Balancing opportunities for all students, including those with disabilities or from disadvantaged communities, is a fundamental challenge. Integrating sports into the curriculum without disrupting academic schedules is complex. Coordinators must work closely with academic departments to ensure that sports activities complement academic priorities rather than compete with. Achieving this balance is key to the success of the integration. Recruiting and retaining qualified sports coaches and instructors can be a hurdle. Training and professional development opportunities are essential to ensure that coaches are equipped to deliver effective and safe sports programs. Addressing the need for more qualified personnel is an ongoing challenge. Intensifying sports into the school curriculum in the Philippines is a journey filled with challenges and opportunities. School coordinators play a pivotal role in navigating these complexities and finding innovative solutions. By addressing these issues with a balanced and informed approach, sports integration can contribute to the holistic development of Filipino students and enrich the educational landscape. Intensifying sports into a school's curriculum can bring numerous benefits, but it also comes with challenges—the issues faced in Sta. Cruz, Davao del Sur, may vary from those in other regions. Still, some common problems

and considerations when implementing sports into the curriculum include Many schools need more sports facilities, equipment, and qualified coaches. This can hinder the effective integration of sports. In a crowded curriculum, sports often compete with academic subjects for students' time. Balancing the two can be a challenge. Scheduling regular sports activities can be challenging due to conflicts with academic classes, exams, and other school events. Ensuring the safety of students during sports activities is crucial. Schools must invest in safety measures, proper equipment, and first-aid training for staff. Some students may need to gain skills or interest in traditional sports. Schools must consider how to be inclusive by offering various sports options or physical activities that cater to a wide range of interests and abilities. Measuring the impact of sports on students' physical and mental development can be challenging. Establishing clear assessment criteria and collecting relevant data is vital. Integrating sports into the curriculum often requires the support and involvement of parents and the local community. Engaging them can be difficult. Ensuring that both male and female students have equal opportunities in sports can be a challenge due to gender stereotypes and societal expectations. Teachers need proper training to effectively integrate sports into the curriculum. Many educators may not have expertise in coaching or sports instruction. Schools may need to allocate time for teacher training, planning sports events, and maintaining sports facilities. Building a long-term plan for the integration of sports into the curriculum is crucial. It must be sustainable and not just a one-time effort. Especially in the context of a pandemic, health considerations are paramount. Schools must adhere to safety guidelines to protect students during sports activities. To address these issues, school coordinators in Sta. Cruz, Davao del Sur, can consider collaborating with local sports organizations and the community to pool resources;

developing a comprehensive plan for integrating sports that includes scheduling, safety measures, and teacher training; promoting a culture of inclusivity, ensuring that all students have opportunities to participate in sports; advocating for gender equity in sports programs; evaluating the effectiveness of sports integration through regular assessments and data collection, encouraging parents and the community to actively support and participate in sports events and adhering to public health guidelines for safe sports participation. Intensifying sports into school curricula has long been recognized as a valuable component of holistic education, fostering physical health, social skills, and cognitive development among students. However, the extent to which sports are incorporated into educational systems varies widely across regions and institutions. In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on intensifying sports within the curriculum, driven by evolving educational philosophies, societal demands, and research highlighting the multifaceted benefits of sports participation for students. This study aimed to explore the perspectives of school coordinators on the intensification of sports within the curriculum. School coordinators play a pivotal role in shaping and implementing educational policies, including those related to sports programming. By understanding their perspectives, insights can be gained into the opportunities, challenges, and potential strategies associated with enhancing sports within the educational framework. The intensification of sports in the curriculum encompasses various aspects, including increasing the frequency and duration of physical education classes, diversifying sports offerings, integrating sports-related content into academic subjects, and promoting extracurricular sports participation. These efforts align with broader objectives such as promoting physical fitness, enhancing academic performance, fostering teamwork and leadership skills, and addressing issues like childhood obesity and

sedentary lifestyles. This also examined the perspectives of school coordinators through qualitative research methods, including interviews and surveys. By gathering firsthand accounts from these key stakeholders, a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing the intensification of sports in the curriculum can be attained. Additionally, by exploring diverse perspectives from school coordinators across different educational settings, insights can be gained into the contextual factors shaping the implementation of sports-related initiatives. This re-

search can generate valuable insights to inform educational policymakers, administrators, teachers, and other stakeholders involved in shaping school curricula. By understanding the perspectives of school coordinators, informed decisions can be made regarding the design, implementation, and evaluation of sports-related initiatives within educational settings. Ultimately, the goal is to promote the holistic development of students by recognizing the importance of sports within the educational landscape.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The phenomenological inquiry in the study entitled "Intensifying Sports in the Curriculum: Through the Perspectives of School Coordinators" was to explore and understand the lived experiences, perceptions, and perspectives of school coordinators involved in integrating sports into the school curriculum. To delve into school coordinators' profound insights and experiences as they navigate the complex landscape of sports integration. This inquiry sought to uncover the essence of their experiences, challenges, and successes in this transformative educational journey. To comprehend the motivations and values that drive school coordinators in Davao Del Sur to advocate for and implement sports integration. By examining their underlying values and principles, the study aimed to reveal what propels their commitment to this educational initiative. To identify the challenges and obstacles school coordinators face in integrating sports into the curriculum and explore the strategies and solutions they employ to address these challenges. This insight is critical for refining the integration process. To provide valuable data that can inform educational policies, practices, and decision-making related to sports integration. The study's findings can serve as a foundation for improving the integration process and making it more effective and inclusive. To contribute to the holistic development of students by ensuring that sports become an integral part of their educational experience. By understanding the experiences of school coordinators, the study aimed to enhance the benefits that students derive from sports integration. To amplify the voices of school coordinators, allowing them to share their perspectives, challenges, and achievements in the journey of sports integration. This research sought to recognize their pivotal role in shaping the educational landscape. To enrich the educational landscape and beyond by shedding light on the unique issues and opportunities related to sports integration. This understanding can inspire innovative approaches and contribute to developing well-rounded, empowered students. In essence, the purpose of this phenomenological inquiry was to unearth the lived experiences and perspectives of school coordinators engaged in integrating sports into the curriculum. By doing so, the study aimed to provide a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of this educational transformation and its impact on students, schools, and the broader community.

1.2. Research Questions—The study was intended to gain the perspectives of sports coordinators in intensifying sports into the curriculum. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of school coordinators on intensifying sports in the curriculum?

- (2) How do school coordinators cope with the challenges of intensifying sports in the curriculum?
- (3) What are the insights gained from the findings of this study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following term was operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Intensifying sports in the curriculum. Intensifying sports into the curriculum includes sports and physical activities as an integral part of the formal educational program in schools and educational institutions. It means that sports, physical education, and related activities are not treated as separate or extracurricular endeavors but are instead incorporated into the regular academic curriculum. This intensification recognizes the importance of physical fitness, well-being, and the development of motor skills as essential components of a holistic education. Sports and physical education classes were scheduled alongside traditional academic subjects within the school day.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The results of this study were significant to the following: Policymakers are responsible for setting the framework for curriculum integration. Develop and revise educational policies that incorporate sports into the curriculum. Allocate resources and funding for sports programs. Ensure that curriculum standards are aligned with sports integration. Establish guidelines for evaluation and assessment; School heads were responsible for implementing policies at the school level and overseeing daily operations. Allocate time and resources within the school schedule for sports activities. Recruit and support qualified sports instructors. Ensure that sports facilities are well-maintained. Promote a culture of sports and physical activity within the school. Teachers were on the front lines of curriculum delivery and played a crucial role in engaging students in sports education. Teach sports-related subjects or modules as part of the curriculum. Create lesson plans that align with academic and physical education objectives. Provide guidance and coaching to students during sports activities. Assess and evaluate student performance in sports; Learners are the primary beneficiaries of sports integration, and their active participation is essential. Actively participate in sports activities and adhere to safety guidelines. Show enthusiasm and commitment to sports education. Attend classes and engage in both theoretical and practical aspects of sports education. Demonstrate sportsmanship and fair play; Research enthusiasts. Researchers and educators contribute to developing and improving sports education in the curriculum. They conduct research on the effectiveness of sports integration in education. They develop evidence-based practices and educational resources for sports curricula. They share research findings with educators and policymakers. They continuously update and improve sports-related curricular materials and teaching methods. The successful integration of sports into the curriculum relies on collaboration and coordination among these key stakeholders. Policymakers need to create a conducive environment, school heads need to facilitate the implementation, teachers need to deliver the curriculum effectively, students need to engage actively, and researchers need to provide insights for continuous improvement. When all these roles and duties are fulfilled, the benefits of sports in education can be maximized, including improved physical health, academic performance, and the development of essential life skills.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—

This study is anchored on goal setting and progress monitoring of Curriculum Theory by Ralph Tyler, Joseph Schwab, Elliot Eisner. Curriculum theory can help you investigate how sports fit into the school's curriculum and educational goal. This lens allows you to explore the design, implementation, and evaluation of sports-related curriculum components. Sing Curriculum Theory, as proposed by influential figures like Ralph Tyler, Joseph Schwab, and Elliot Eisner, in your study on integrating sports into the curriculum through the perspective of school coordinators can provide valuable insights into the process. Ralph Tyler's *Basic Principles*: Tyler is known for his essential principles of curriculum development, including defining clear objectives, selecting appropriate content, organizing learning experiences, and evaluating the curriculum. Apply these principles to the integration of sports in the curriculum. For example, investigate how school coordinators define the objectives of sports integration, select sports-related content, design learning experiences, and evaluate the effectiveness of these components. Joseph Schwab's *Practical Curriculum Theory*: Schwab emphasizes the importance of the practical aspects of curriculum. He believes that curriculum should not be an abstract concept but a practical guide for teachers and coordinators. Use Schwab's perspective to explore how school coordinators operationalize the inclusion of sports in the curriculum. Elliot Eisner's *Connoisseurship and Criticism*: Eisner's curriculum theory focuses on the importance of artistry in curriculum design. He suggests that educators should be curriculum "connoisseurs" who can appreciate and critique the curriculum like a work of art. Use the curriculum theory lens to investigate the design of sports-related curriculum components. Explore the implementation process. Evaluate the sports-related curriculum components. Curriculum theory encourages alignment with educational goals. Analyze how school coordinators ensure that the integration of sports aligns with the broader educational mission of the school. By applying Curriculum Theory in your study, you can delve into the design, implementation, and evaluation of sports-related curriculum components while considering how they contribute to achieving educational goals. This lens provides a structured framework for exploring the relationship between sports and the broader curriculum in a school setting. Sport Education is a curriculum and instruction model designed for delivery within physical education. Modifications can suit each age category, activity, or setting. It is most effective with games-based activities and with participants who have a good base level of competence. It was intended to provide children and youth with more authentic and enjoyable sports experiences than what we typically see in traditional physical education lessons. Daryl Siedentop developed and introduced this model in 1984, and it has since been adapted and successfully implemented across physical education programs nationally and internationally. Students participate as members of teams in seasons that are longer than the usual physical education unit. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. This study conceptualized the experiences and coping mechanisms of school coordinators in integrating sports into the curriculum and insights drawn from its findings. The study focuses on these three interconnected variables to explore coordinators' experiences in their journey to integrating sports into the curriculum.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. The explored facts and

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

knowledge in this study necessitate the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. *Ontology.* This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. Creswell (2012) pointed out that reality was subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and inter-

pretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study was coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. The researcher carefully coded the participants' responses to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and prohibited personal bias as the study progressed. *Epistemology.* This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher would attempt to lessen the distance between themselves and the participants. It was suggested that being a researcher, it was expected that time was spent

in the field with participants and become an 'insider.' It was assumed that the researcher established a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) states that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggested that the researcher openly discussed values that shaped the narrative and included their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. The researcher upheld the dignity and value of every piece of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. The researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully understood the answers in light of the participants' interpretation.

Rhetoric meant reporting reality through the eyes of my research participants. The researcher used personal voice and qualitative terms such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability instead of internal and external validity and objectivity. Patton (2000) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks, "What

is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people? This research study aimed to work well with this definition in trying to understand the coordinators' perspectives on integrating sports into the curriculum. Guba (2007) pointed out that the researcher needs to prepare for an investigation greater in depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested that the information be viewed as "the tip of the iceberg." The researcher implemented the qualitative research method of phenomenology to allow for the exploration of the teachers' experiences in continuing professional development. Burns and Grove (2003) stated that phenomenology is a philosophy, an approach or perspective to living, learning and doing research". The goal of phenomenological research was to capture lived experiences, find meaning that may or may not be known to the person who experienced them, and describe the phenomenon through a composite narrative. For the qualitative researcher, the only reality was the reality of the participants involved in the research situations constructed.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—A phenomenological approach was chosen for this study, using qualitative methodology. This study used an in-depth interview. The researcher conducted the interview using an interview guide made by the researcher, which the participants answered based on their experiences and practices that were related to this study. In-depth interviews were a qualitative research technique that involved conducting intensive individual interviews with a few respondents to explore their perspectives on a particu-

lar idea, program, or situation (Boyce and Neale, 2006). Interviews are primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. A phenomenological approach was used to gain a broader insight. Phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon for investigatory inquiry. (Creswell, 2013).

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—

The study utilized a qualitative research method employing a phenomenological qualitative design. According to Lester, phenomenological research is concerned with the study of experiences from the perspective of the individual, "bracketing" taken-for-granted assumptions and usual ways of perceiving. The phenomenological approach is based on a paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity. It emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. Thus, it was powerful for understanding subjective experiences, gaining insights into participants' motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Qualitative research was mainly associated with words, language, and experiences rather than measurements, statistics, and numerical figures. Qualitative research refers to the inductive, holistic, epic, subjective, and process-oriented methods used to understand, interpret, describe, and develop a theory on phenomena or settings. It was a systematic, subjective approach used to describe life experiences and give them meaning (Burns Grove 2003). The phenomenological research design was selected in this study to collect data on teachers' perspectives on integrating sports into the curriculum. This research approach deepened the understanding of nature and the meaning of everyday experiences. Corbetta (2003) stated that the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help to grasp the subject's perspective. Bryman (2012) posited that personal and detailed stories could be told through interviews or face-to-face discussions, focusing on how the interviewee understands and explains different phenomena. The researcher aimed to draw an in-depth study of the perspectives and experiences of the coordinators on integrating sports into the curriculum. Qualitative research was interested in understanding how people interpret their experiences, how they construct their worlds, and what meaning they attribute to their experiences" (Merriam, 2009). This form of research would provide a deep understanding of the subject and results in enhanced explanatory power. The researcher becomes "a part of the world they study; the knower and the known are taken to be inseparable" (Hatch, 2002). Because of the researcher's involvement, however, "much qualitative research is subjective..." (Wrench, Thomas-Maddox, Richmond, and McCroskey, 2008). Bloomberg and Volpe (2008) described qualitative research as "idea generation." Its design was proposed up front, but it is open and emergent rather than rigid and fixed to permit exploration. It uses small samples purposefully. It takes place within natural contexts, and real-world situations are studied as they unfold. Its framework allows for flexibility and creativity. The qualitative research explored and described coordinators' perspectives, experiences, and coping mechanisms regarding the challenges of integrating sports into the curriculum. The research technique used was a modified Van Kaam method described by Moustakas (2000) based on recorded and transcribed interviews using semi-structured questions to capture the coordinators' experiences. Specifically, phenomenology was the study of the subjective experiences of others. It researched the world through another person's eyes by discovering how they interpret their experiences. It describes the meaning of the lived experiences of several individuals about a concept or a phenomenon. Phenomenology explores the structures of consciousness in human experiences, as Polkinghorne (2000) noted. This involved procedures which the qualitative researchers should follow. First, the researcher wrote research questions that would explore the meaning of life experiences for individuals and asked individuals to describe these experiences. The researcher collected data from individuals who

had experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via lengthy interviews. Next, the data analysis involved horizontalization that was extracting significant statements from transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement would fall under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience – both the textual description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated the meaning of the experience here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected in the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket their own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when their observations were incorporated into the study. Accordingly, Hycner (2008) phenomenology in business research studies ideas were generated from the abundant amount of data using induction and human interests, as well as stakeholder perspective may reflect on the study. A study that attempted to explore sports coordinators' experiences in integrating sports into the curriculum via conducting in-depth interviews is a relevant example of research with a phenomenology philoso-

phy. Advantages associated with phenomenology include a better understanding of meanings attached by people and its contribution to developing new theories. Its disadvantages include difficulties with analysis and interpretation, usually lower levels of validity and reliability compared to positivism, and more time and other resources required for data collection (Hycner, 2008). Similarly, Schutz (2010) stressed that the purpose of the phenomenological approach was to illuminate the specific to identify phenomena through how the actors perceive them in a situation. In the human sphere, this translates typically into gathering 'deep' information and perceptions through inductive, qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions, and participant observation and representing it from the perspective of the research participant(s). Phenomenology is concerned with the study of experience from the perspective of the individual, 'bracketing' taken-for-granted assumptions, and usual ways of perceiving. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were dominant in understanding the subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. The researcher's purpose was to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research since the focal point of this study is to uncover coordinators' perspectives in intensifying sports into the curriculum.

2.4. Research Participants—The key informants of this study were the selected sports coordinators of Sta. Cruz North District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The researcher utilized ten (10) teachers for qualitative participants in an in-depth interview (IDE) who were

randomly selected from different elementary schools in the district. The informants should have been school sports coordinators for at least one school year, teaching three or more years with their permanent appointment regardless of sex and marital status. Data were collected

through the one-on-one interview process and qualitative survey instruments. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study. It was also known as judg-

mental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants were purposefully done to ensure that the findings were authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations were of paramount importance in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participant groups addressed in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most critical parts of the research. The researcher also adheres to promoting the aims of the research, imparting factual knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. Research is essential to society. This study focuses on the social value of sports coordinators' experiences. Thus, the social problem that pushed the researcher's interest was the challenges they experienced while integrating sports into the curriculum. This study could serve as a basis for higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Informed Consent. Gaining the trust and support of research participants is critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007 as cited by Pellerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The informed consent letter aims to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and identify the anticipated information that the informants are expected to provide. All participants were then required to sign and return the consent letter to the re-

searcher before participating. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to participate ensured that participation in the research was entirely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants were lodged in the appendices of this study. The Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study were deemed capable of answering the research instrument because they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher then assured the participants that they could easily be reached through their contact number and address in case there were any clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. This was done to answer the respondents' possible questions. Furthermore, if respondents experienced possible discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher had to ensure the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered conveniently. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality, as well as risk minimization. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not

to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output from this study was kept anonymous. Furthermore, all the issues were given consideration so that there would be no conflict of interest among the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were then briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any type of communication about the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they would benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. The study's results can then be accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and placed on CD or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher. Also, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers would be aware of the significance of the research and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can request to be allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. The participants could amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ pseudonyms and change names or non-significant dates to pro-

tect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured the possession of the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher had completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, the last requirement to obtain the researcher's master's degree. They were qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. Also, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to complete the study successfully within the specified time, and they were equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee would help enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. The researcher also had to ensure that they had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study would not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher deemed it necessary to express their great pleasure in their whole-hearted participation in this study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by adequately citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said in their own way. Understand the study context and avoid copying and pasting the text verbatim from the reference paper. Always use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, they would assure them of honesty in working on the manuscript and that there was no intentional misrepresentation in the study and making up of data and results or purposefully putting forward conclusions that are not accurate.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher—*

The researcher wrote a letter asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. After this, another letter of permission was secured and submitted to the participants. Upon approval, I used the forms of data collection prescribed in the qualitative design. In this study, an in-depth interview was recorded. The researcher needs to understand the subjective interaction between the study participants. The researcher heavily relied on naturalistic methods (interviewing and audio recording) and the interpretive paradigm. Interpretive approaches rely heavily on naturalistic methods like interviewing, observation, and analysis of existing texts. These methods ensure an adequate dialog between the researchers and those with whom they interact to construct a meaningful reality collaboratively. Yin, as cited by Aquilam (2014), suggested numerous forms of data col-

lection, including documents, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant observation, and physical artifacts. In order to have legitimate and trustworthy data on sports coordinators' perspectives, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview and focus group discussion. This interview aimed to explore the experiences of school sports coordinators in intensifying sports in the curriculum. The participants were encouraged to express their answers most comfortably. The interview with the teacher was transcribed word for word. Lastly, the researcher analyzed the data collected using discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Creswell (2007) suggested that to succeed in the study, the data must be stored so that they can be easily found and protected from damage and loss.

2.7. Data Collection—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument, which explains the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher waited for the response of the SDS before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview us-

ing the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and thematizing. After the transcription, the data were categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual data within the participants were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell’s Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research were similar codes aggregated together to form a significant idea in the database. Familiarization with the data is common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis. It involves generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and concep-

tual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data pertinent to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each individual theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage, the data was sifted, charted, and sorted by key issues and themes. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher was familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes) and gained an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher becomes aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and notes them.

Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may only be able to review some of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set was utilized. The choice would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, a mix of methods, such as interviews, documents, and observations, could be used. The second stage of identifying a thematic framework occurs after familiarization when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes issues; however, at this stage, the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and topics. To achieve this, the researcher would use the notes taken during the familiarization stage. The key issues, concepts, and themes that the participants expressed would form the basis of a thematic framework used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

identifying portions or sections of the data that correspond to a particular theme. This process was applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For the sake of convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used for the indexing references and annotated in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping and interpretation, involved the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phe-

nomenon, thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994:186). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflect the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the participants’ actual attitudes, beliefs, and values.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—

The concepts of validity and reliability were relatively foreign to qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness, which consists of components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility refers to the extent to which a research account is believable and appropriate, particularly regarding the level of agreement between participants and the researcher. The notion of credibility was most often associated with the framework presented by Yvonna Lincoln and Egon Guba. Transferability is the degree to which qualitative research results can be transferred to other contexts or settings with other respondents. The re-

searcher facilitates the transferability judgment by a potential user through thick description. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and ensure that the findings were consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. Conformability refers to the objectivity of research during data collection and data analysis. There needs to be congruency between two or more independent persons about the data's accuracy, relevance, or meaning (Polit and Beck, 2012). Conformability also indicates a means to demonstrate quality.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents and discusses the study's results with reference to its aim. It also discusses the themes that emerged from the data gathered. The results present the description and background of the participants who were assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

3.1. Experiences of school coordinators on intensifying sports in the curriculum—Intensifying sports in the curriculum can vary widely depending on factors such as the resources available, support from administration, community engagement, and the school's overall culture. Intensifying sports in the curriculum often leads to higher levels of student engagement. Many students are enthusiastic about sports and enjoy participating in organized activities during the school day. Integrating more sports into the curriculum can improve students' physical health. Regular physical activity is essential for overall well-being, and incorporating sports into the school day helps ensure that students have opportunities to be active. One common challenge faced by school coordinators is the need for more resources. Intensifying sports in the curriculum may require additional equipment, facilities, and funding from coaching staff. Securing adequate resources can be a significant barrier

for some schools. School coordinators must strike a balance between academic and athletic priorities. While sports are valuable for physical health and personal development, they should not overshadow academic pursuits. Coordinators must ensure that students have time for both sports and academics. Intensifying sports in the curriculum provides an opportunity to promote inclusivity and diversity. Coordinators should strive to offer a variety of sports that appeal to students with different interests and abilities. Additionally, efforts should be made to ensure that sports programs are accessible to all students, regardless of background or ability level. School coordinators work to build partnerships with local sports organizations, businesses, and community members to support their efforts to intensify sports in the curriculum. These partnerships can provide additional resources, expertise, and opportunities for students. Intensifying sports in the curriculum raises con-

cerns about equity, particularly if certain students face barriers to participation. Coordinators should be mindful of these issues and work to address them through strategies such as offering scholarships, providing transportation, and ensuring access to necessary equipment and facilities. School coordinators face challenges in measuring the impact of intensified sports in the curriculum. While outcomes such as increased physical activity levels and improved student engagement are desirable, they can be difficult

to quantify. Coordinators may need to develop assessment tools and collect data to evaluate the effectiveness of their sports programs. Overall, the experiences of school coordinators on intensifying sports in the curriculum are multifaceted, involving both opportunities and challenges. By addressing issues such as resource allocation, equity, and community partnerships, coordinators can create enriching sports programs that benefit students both academically and physically.

3.1.1. Challenges with the Resources— The participants describe that challenges with resources can significantly impact the experiences of school coordinators when intensifying sports in the curriculum. One of the most common challenges is limited funding for sports programs. School budgets may already be stretched thin, leaving little room for additional expenditures on equipment, facilities, coaching staff, and transportation. Coordinators may need to get creative with fundraising efforts or seek external funding sources to supplement their budgets. Many schools face a shortage of adequate sports facilities. This could include insufficient gymnasium space, outdated or unsafe equipment, or a lack of playing fields or tracks. Coordinators may need to find alternative solutions, such as partnering with local community centers or utilizing outdoor spaces, to accommodate their sports programs. Providing appropriate sports equipment for various activities can be costly. Schools may struggle to afford items such as uniforms, balls, mats, goals, and safety gear. Coordinators may need to prioritize their equipment purchases based on the sports being offered and explore options like equipment rentals or donations from community organizations. Intensifying sports in the curriculum often requires additional coaching staff and personnel to oversee activities and ensure student safety. However, hiring quali-

fied coaches and instructors within budget constraints can be difficult. Coordinators may need to recruit volunteers, utilize existing staff members with sports backgrounds, or provide training opportunities for current staff to fill coaching roles. Transportation can be a significant barrier for students, especially if they need to travel off-campus for practices or competitions. Coordinators may struggle to secure reliable transportation options within their budget, potentially limiting the scope of their sports programs. Creative solutions like carpooling, public transportation subsidies, or partnering with local transportation providers may be necessary. The participant also stated that even if schools have existing sports facilities and equipment, there may be ongoing costs associated with maintenance and upkeep. Budget constraints can make allocating funds for repairs, upgrades, and general maintenance challenging, leading to deteriorating conditions over time. Coordinators may need to prioritize maintenance tasks and advocate for additional funding to ensure the longevity of their sports programs. Limited resources can exacerbate equity issues within sports programs. Students from lower-income backgrounds may face barriers to participation due to the cost of equipment, fees, and transportation. Coordinators must be proactive in addressing these disparities by providing financial assistance, offering scholarship opportunities,

and ensuring equal access to resources for all students. Addressing these challenges requires creativity, resourcefulness, and collaboration among school administrators, community stakeholders, and the broader school community. By

3.1.2. Balancing Academic and Athletic Priorities—While facing challenges with resources is a significant concern for school coordinators when intensifying sports in the curriculum. One of the biggest challenges in balancing academic and athletic priorities is managing students' time effectively. Intensifying sports in the curriculum means students spend more time on athletic activities, potentially cutting into time they could dedicate to academic studies. Coordinators must work closely with teachers and coaches to develop schedules that allow students to excel both academically and athletically without sacrificing one for the other. Intensifying sports in the curriculum requires additional academic support for student-athletes to help them maintain their academic performance. However, limited resources can make it difficult to provide extra tutoring, study halls, or academic advisors for student-athletes. Coordinators must find creative ways to offer academic support within their budget constraints, such as utilizing peer tutoring programs or leveraging technology for online resources. Student-athletes often face competing priorities between academic responsibilities and sports commitments. Coordinators must help students prioritize their time effectively, emphasizing the importance of academic success while still allowing them to participate fully in sports activities. This may involve setting clear expectations, communicating with teachers and coaches, and providing time management resources for students. Limited resources can impact the availability and quality of facilities and equipment for sports programs. This can directly affect student-athletes' abil-

advocating for adequate resources and implementing innovative solutions, school coordinators can overcome these obstacles and create meaningful sports experiences for students.

ity to train effectively and may lead to safety concerns if facilities are outdated or in disrepair. Coordinators must advocate for adequate funding to maintain and upgrade facilities, ensuring that student-athletes have access to safe and appropriate equipment for their training and competitions. A lack of resources can also affect the availability and quality of coaching staff for sports programs. Schools may struggle to hire experienced coaches or provide adequate compensation for coaching positions, leading to challenges in providing effective coaching and mentorship for student-athletes. Coordinators must work within budget constraints to recruit and retain qualified coaching staff, potentially exploring options like volunteer coaches or partnerships with community organizations. Limited resources can impact transportation options for student-athletes traveling to and from practices, games, and competitions. This can create logistical challenges for coordinating schedules and ensuring all students have access to transportation, particularly if practices or games are held off-campus. Coordinators must work with school administrators, parents, and community stakeholders to find affordable transportation solutions that meet the needs of student-athletes while staying within budgetary constraints. In summary, balancing academic and athletic priorities while facing challenges with resources requires careful planning, collaboration, and creative problem-solving from school coordinators. By prioritizing student well-being and advocating for adequate resources, coordinators can create a supportive environment where student-athletes can excel both academically and athletically.

3.1.3. Increased Student Engagement—The participants work with their students and discover student engagement is often a positive outcome of intensifying sports in the curriculum, and school coordinators play a crucial role in facilitating this engagement. Intensifying sports in the curriculum provides students with a wider range of opportunities to engage in physical activity and athletic pursuits. Coordinators may introduce new sports programs or expand existing ones to cater to different interests and skill levels. This variety encourages more students to participate and find activities that resonate with them. Coordinators strive to create an inclusive environment where all students feel welcome and encouraged to participate in sports activities. They offer inclusive sports programs that accommodate students of diverse backgrounds, abilities, and interests. This inclusivity fosters a sense of belonging and encourages students who may not have previously been involved in sports to participate. Coordinators empower students to take on leadership roles within sports programs. This could involve roles such as team captains, student coaches, or sports club officers. By giving students opportunities to lead and contribute to the organization and management of sports activities, coordinators foster a sense of ownership and investment in the programs. Coordinators actively promote sports programs and events to increase student awareness and participation. They use various strategies such as organizing pep rallies, distributing informational flyers, hosting recruitment events, and leveraging social media platforms to engage students and generate interest in sports activities. Intensifying sports in the curriculum often involves providing students opportunities to compete against other schools or participate in inter-school leagues and tournaments. Coordinators organize these competitive events and encourage students to represent their school teams, fostering a sense of pride and school spirit among participants. Coordinators actively seek input from students to understand their interests, preferences, and needs regarding sports activities. They may conduct surveys, hold focus groups, or establish student advisory committees to gather feedback and involve students in decision-making processes related to sports programming. Incorporating student feedback helps ensure that sports activities are relevant and engaging for the student body. Coordinators recognize and celebrate student achievements in sports through various means such as awards ceremonies, athlete of the month/year recognitions, and public announcements. Recognizing students' efforts and accomplishments reinforces positive behavior and encourages continued participation in sports activities. Some coordinators explore ways to integrate sports activities with the academic curriculum to enhance student engagement. This could involve incorporating sports-related themes or topics into classroom lessons, organizing interdisciplinary projects related to sports, or offering academic credit for participation in sports programs. Overall, school coordinators play a pivotal role in fostering increased student engagement through sports by creating inclusive environments, providing diverse opportunities, promoting participation, incorporating student feedback, and recognizing student achievements. By prioritizing student involvement and creating positive experiences, coordinators contribute to the overall success and impact of sports programs within the school community. A study by Standage et al. (2006), providing opportunities for student choice and autonomy in sports participation can enhance intrinsic motivation and student engagement. School coordinators may offer various sports options and allow students to select activities based on their preferences, promoting a sense of ownership and autonomy in their sporting pursuits. Based on Figure 3, three themes emerged from the responses of the participants, which were challenges with resources, balancing aca-

Fig. 3. Emerging themes on the experiences of school coordinators on intensifying sports in the curriculum

demical and athletic priorities, and increased student engagement. As to resource challenges, school coordinators frequently need more funding, affecting their ability to procure necessary resources for sports programs. This includes financial constraints for equipment, facilities, coaching staff, and transportation. Limited resources may result in outdated or insufficient facilities and equipment, impacting the quality of sports programs and student experiences. Coordinators often need to navigate budget constraints by seeking alternative funding sources, negotiating partnerships with local businesses

or community organizations, or creatively allocating existing resources. In balancing academic and athletic priorities, coordinators face the challenge of striking a balance between academic commitments and athletic pursuits for students. Intensifying sports in the curriculum requires effective time management strategies to ensure that students can excel academically while participating in sports activities. Providing academic support for student-athletes, such as tutoring, study halls, or flexible scheduling, becomes essential to maintain

3.2. Coping Mechanisms with the challenges of intensifying sports in the curriculum—As educators, they are embarking on a journey to cultivate the love of coping mechanisms as essential for school coordinators to navigate the challenges they face when intensifying sports in the curriculum. Coordinators can cope with limited resources by strategically budgeting and prioritizing expenses. They allocate funds to areas with the greatest impact, such as essential equipment, safety gear, and transportation for student-athletes. Coordinators can explore external funding sources such

as grants, sponsorships from local businesses, or partnerships with community organizations. Seeking financial support from external sources can help alleviate budget constraints and provide additional resources for sports programs. Organizing fundraising events and initiatives can help coordinators generate additional funds for sports programs. This could include activities like bake sales, car washes, or sports-themed events that involve students, parents, and the community. Coordinators can leverage the support of volunteers to assist with coaching, officiating, or organizing sports events. Recruit-

ing volunteers from the community, including parents, alumni, and sports enthusiasts, can help supplement coaching staff and alleviate staffing constraints. Establishing partnerships with local sports organizations, community centers, and recreational facilities can provide access to resources such as training facilities, equipment rentals, and coaching expertise. Collaborating with external partners can expand the opportunities available to students and enhance the quality of sports programs. Coordinators can maximize the use of existing resources within the school community. This could involve repurposing

underutilized facilities, sharing equipment between sports programs, or collaborating with other school departments to share resources and reduce costs. Coordinators can advocate for the needs of sports programs within the school administration and communicate effectively with stakeholders to raise awareness of challenges and potential solutions. By articulating the importance of sports in the curriculum and highlighting the benefits for students, coordinators can garner support for allocating resources to sports programs.

3.2.1. Advocacy and Communication—The participants believed that advocacy and communication play a crucial role as coping mechanisms for school coordinators when facing challenges in intensifying sports in the curriculum. School coordinators can advocate for the necessary resources needed to support sports programs by effectively communicating the benefits to school administrators, stakeholders, and the broader community. This may involve presenting data on the positive impact of sports on student outcomes, such as improved academic performance, enhanced physical health, and increased student engagement. Coordinators can build support networks within the school community by engaging with teachers, parents, alumni, and local community members who share an interest in promoting sports. By fostering positive relationships and collaboration, coordinators can gain allies who can advocate for and contribute to the success of sports programs. Coordinators can educate stakeholders, including parents, teachers, and school board members, about the importance of sports in the curriculum and the challenges faced in intensifying sports programs. Providing information on the benefits of sports for student development and well-being can help garner support and understanding for the need for resources and

investment in sports programs. Coordinators can raise awareness about the challenges and needs of sports programs through various communication channels, such as school newsletters, websites, social media platforms, and community meetings. By sharing stories, testimonials, and success stories of student-athletes, coordinators can illustrate the value of sports programs and generate public support. Furthermore, the participants also stressed that coordinators can engage in dialogue with school administrators, teachers, and other stakeholders to address concerns, gather feedback, and collaborate on solutions to challenges. Open communication channels allow for constructive discussions and the development of strategies to overcome obstacles. Coordinators can empower student-athletes to advocate for their sports programs by providing opportunities for them to share their experiences, voice their needs, and participate in decision-making processes. Student-led advocacy initiatives, such as writing letters to school administrators or organizing advocacy events, can be powerful tools for raising awareness and influencing change. Coordinators can leverage professional associations and networks related to sports management, education, and athletics to access resources, share best practices, and advocate for support. Membership in professional

organizations provides opportunities for professional development, networking, and advocacy on behalf of sports programs. Coordinators can measure and communicate the impact of sports programs on student outcomes to demonstrate their effectiveness and justify the need for resources. This may involve collecting data on participation rates, academic performance, student satisfaction, and other relevant metrics to

provide evidence of the value of sports in the curriculum. By utilizing advocacy and communication strategies effectively, school coordinators can effectively cope with challenges in intensifying sports in the curriculum and work towards creating a supportive and sustainable environment for sports programs within their schools.

3.2.2. Professional Development—The participants further conveyed that professional development is a valuable coping mechanism for school coordinators facing challenges in intensifying sports in the curriculum. Participating in professional development opportunities such as workshops, conferences, and training sessions related to sports management, coaching techniques, and program development can enhance coordinators' skills and knowledge. This enables them to better navigate challenges and effectively manage sports programs. Professional development events provide opportunities for coordinators to network with peers, experts, and stakeholders in the field of sports education and athletics. Building professional relationships and collaborating with others facing similar challenges can offer support, share best practices, and generate new ideas for overcoming obstacles. Professional development often includes access to resources such as research findings, curriculum materials, and tools for program evaluation and improvement. Coordinators can leverage these resources to enhance the quality and effectiveness of sports programs within their schools. The participant also believes that sports education and athletics are constantly evolving, with new trends, techniques, and best practices emerging. Professional development allows coordinators to stay updated on these developments, ensuring that their sports programs remain relevant and aligned with current standards and practices. Professional de-

velopment opportunities can help coordinators develop their leadership skills, including communication, decision-making, problem-solving, and conflict resolution. Strong leadership abilities enable coordinators to effectively manage challenges, inspire others, and drive positive change within their sports programs. Engaging in professional development is an ongoing process that allows coordinators to continue learning and growing in their roles. By seeking out new knowledge, skills, and perspectives, coordinators can adapt to evolving challenges and contribute to the continuous improvement of sports programs. Participation in professional development activities demonstrates a commitment to professional growth and excellence, which can enhance coordinators' credibility and reputation within their field. Professional development opportunities may also contribute to career advancement opportunities and professional recognition within the education and sports communities. Professional development can also include opportunities for self-care and well-being, such as sessions on stress management, work-life balance, and resilience-building. Taking care of their own well-being enables coordinators to cope better with challenges, maintain motivation, and sustain their effectiveness in their roles. Overall, professional development serves as a valuable coping mechanism for school coordinators facing challenges in intensifying sports in the curriculum. By investing in their own growth and development,

coordinators can enhance their skills, expand their professional networks, stay updated on best practices, and ultimately improve the qual-

ity and impact of sports programs within their schools.

3.2.3. Community Partnerships—The educational journey community partnerships serve as effective coping mechanisms for school coordinators facing challenges in intensifying sports in the curriculum. Community partnerships provide access to resources that may not be readily available within the school, such as sports facilities, equipment, coaching expertise, and financial support. Collaborating with local sports organizations, businesses, and community centers allows coordinators to leverage these resources to enhance sports programs despite limited school resources. Partnering with community organizations that have sports facilities and equipment can alleviate the burden on the school’s budget. Coordinators can negotiate agreements to use these facilities and equipment for practices, games, and competitions, reducing the need for costly investments in building or maintaining sports infrastructure. Community partnerships can provide access to coaching expertise and support from experienced coaches and athletes within the community. Coordinators can collaborate with local sports clubs, associations, or recreational programs to recruit volunteer coaches or arrange coaching clinics for student-athletes, enhancing the quality of coaching and skill development. Community partnerships offer opportunities for financial support and sponsorship from local businesses, organizations, and community members. Coordinators can seek sponsorship deals, donations, or fundraising opportunities to supplement the school’s budget for sports programs, address-

ing financial challenges and ensuring the sustainability of sports initiatives. This finding is congruent with the notion of a comprehensive study by Larson et al. (2019). Professional development programs can provide school coordinators with strategies for effective community engagement. This may include training on outreach methods, communication strategies, and relationship-building techniques to establish and maintain partnerships with local sports organizations, clubs, and community groups. In comprehensive research by Foley Rosenthal (2017), training sessions focused on community engagement can help school coordinators identify potential partners within the community and develop collaborative initiatives to support sports curriculum intensification. Coordinators can learn how to leverage community resources, facilities, and expertise to enhance school sports programming. Based on figure 4, three themes emerged from the participants’ responses: advocacy and communication, professional development, and community partnership on coping mechanisms with the challenges of intensifying sports in the curriculum. Indeed, three prominent themes emerged from the responses regarding coping mechanisms with the challenges of intensifying sports in the curriculum. These themes are advocacy and communication, professional development, and community partnerships. Advocacy and communication are foundational in addressing challenges related to intensifying sports in the curriculum. School coordinators advocate for

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study—The participants shared their educational management insights, and the list was narrowed down

to one to generate the themes. These themes were carefully analyzed and formulated based on informants’ accounts and reflections. The subthemes are shown below:

Fig. 4. Emerging themes on coping mechanisms with the challenges on intensifying sports in the curriculum

3.3.1. Importance of Holistic Approach— The study likely underscores the critical role of contextual relevance in the importance of a holistic approach in educational management, particularly in the context of intensifying sports in the curriculum, underscoring the insights drawn from the findings of the study. A holistic approach recognizes that education encompasses more than just academic achievement. Insights from the study emphasize the importance of providing students with opportunities for physical, social, emotional, and cognitive development through sports programs. Educational management must prioritize a comprehensive approach to student development that addresses these diverse needs. The findings highlight the need to balance academic and non-academic priorities when integrating sports into the curriculum. Educational management must adopt a holistic perspective that values both academic learning and the benefits of sports participation. This involves coordinating schedules, allocating resources, and creating supportive environments that enable students to excel academically while engaging in sports activities. Insights from the study emphasize the importance of acknowledging and accommodating diverse student interests, talents, and learning styles. Educational management should adopt a holistic approach

that provides inclusive sports programs catering to diverse student preferences and abilities. This involves offering diverse sports options, supporting students with varying skill levels, and promoting inclusivity within sports programs. The study findings underscore the positive impact of sports on student well-being and mental health. Educational management must prioritize student well-being by promoting a holistic approach that recognizes the importance of physical activity, social interaction, and emotional support within sports programs. This involves creating environments that foster positive relationships, resilience, and self-confidence among students through sports participation. Insights from the study highlight the role of sports programs in fostering a positive school culture. Educational management should promote a holistic approach that values sports as an integral part of the school experience, contributing to a sense of community, school spirit, and pride among students, teachers, and administrators. This involves promoting inclusivity, celebrating achievements, and encouraging participation in sports activities as essential components of the school culture. The study findings suggest a positive correlation between sports participation and academic performance. Educational management should recognize the potential of

sports programs to enhance academic outcomes and adopt a holistic approach that integrates sports into the curriculum as a complementary component of academic learning. This involves aligning sports programs with educational goals, providing support for student-athletes, and promoting a balance between sports and academics to optimize student success. In summary, a holistic approach in educational management is

essential for effectively integrating sports into the curriculum and promoting comprehensive student development. Insights drawn from the study emphasize the importance of adopting a holistic perspective that values the diverse needs and benefits of sports participation, ultimately contributing to a supportive and enriching educational experience for students.

3.3.2. Resource Management Strategies— The study likely emphasizes the importance of resource management strategies in intensifying sports in the curriculum within educational management. Insights drawn from the study's findings highlight several key resource management strategies. Educational management must strategically allocate budgetary resources to support sports programs effectively. Insights from the study emphasize the importance of prioritizing funding for essential resources such as sports equipment, facilities maintenance, coaching staff, transportation, and academic support services for student-athletes. Educational management should explore opportunities for securing external funding sources to supplement the school's budget for sports programs. Insights from the study suggest that partnerships with local businesses, community organizations, and philanthropic foundations can provide additional financial support for sports initiatives. Coordinators should actively seek grants, sponsorships, and donations to enhance resources for sports programs. Educational management should maximize the use of existing resources within the school community to support sports programs. The study's insights indicate that coordinators can repurpose underutilized facilities, share equipment between sports programs, and collaborate with other school departments to optimize resource utilization. By creatively leveraging existing resources, coordinators can address resource constraints while maintaining

the quality of sports programs. Effective facility management is crucial for optimizing resources in sports programs. Educational management should prioritize maintenance and upgrades of sports facilities to ensure they meet the needs of student-athletes. Insights from the study suggest that coordinators should develop maintenance schedules, conduct regular inspections, and invest in facility improvements to enhance the quality and safety of sports facilities. Educational management should engage volunteers from the school and local community to support sports programs. Insights from the study highlight the value of recruiting volunteer coaches, officials, and support staff to supplement coaching staff and reduce staffing costs. Coordinators should establish volunteer recruitment processes, provide training and support for volunteers, and recognize their contributions to sports programs. Educational management must advocate for the resource needs of sports programs within the school administration and community. Insights from the study suggest that coordinators should effectively communicate the importance of sports in the curriculum, articulate resource requirements, and advocate for adequate funding and support from school administrators, teachers, parents, and community members. By advocating for resource needs, coordinators can ensure that sports programs receive the necessary support to thrive. In summary, resource management strategies are essential for intensifying sports in the curriculum within

educational management. Insights drawn from the study underscore the importance of strategic budget allocation, seeking external funding, maximizing existing resources, efficient facility management, volunteer recruitment, and utilization, and advocating for resource needs to support the success of sports programs. By implementing these resource management strategies, educational management can effectively address resource constraints and enhance the quality of sports programs within schools. One shared: "Masaya ang pagtuturo lalo na kagap may sports intensification." ("Teaching is fun specially when there is sports intensification.") (Teaching is fun especially when there is sports intensification.) ("Teaching is fun especially when there is sports intensification.")

3.3.3. Student-Centered Approach—A student-centered approach is crucial when intensifying sports in the curriculum within educational management. Insights drawn from the findings of the study highlight several key aspects of a student-centered approach. A student-centered approach ensures that sports programs offer inclusive opportunities for all students, regardless of their skill level or background. Insights from the study suggest that coordinators should provide a variety of sports options to cater to diverse student interests and abilities, ensuring that every student has the opportunity to participate and thrive in sports activities. A student-centered approach involves providing individualized support to student-athletes to help them succeed both academically and athletically. Insights from the study indicate that coordinators should offer academic support services such as tutoring, study halls, and flexible scheduling to student-athletes, enabling them to balance their academic and athletic commitments effectively. A student-centered approach empowers student-athletes to take ownership of their sports experiences and de-

(P9)

Research by Shilbury et al. (2013), strategic partnerships with external organizations, such as sports clubs, businesses, and nonprofit organizations, can provide additional resources and support for sports curriculum intensification. Schools can collaborate with partners to access funding, equipment donations, coaching expertise, and promotional opportunities for sports programs. In a study by Hoye et al. (2016), sponsorship agreements with local businesses, corporations, and philanthropic foundations can provide financial support for sports curriculum intensification. Schools may seek sponsorship opportunities for sports teams, events, tournaments, or facility naming rights to generate revenue and offset program costs.

velopment. Insights from the study suggest that coordinators should involve student-athletes in decision-making processes, leadership roles, and advocacy efforts related to sports programs. By empowering student-athletes, coordinators foster a sense of ownership and investment in their sports experiences. A student-centered approach recognizes the unique needs and goals of each student-athlete and provides personalized development opportunities. Insights from the study highlight the importance of offering coaching expertise, skill development programs, and leadership opportunities tailored to individual student-athletes' interests and aspirations. A student-centered approach prioritizes the well-being and holistic development of student-athletes. Insights from the study suggest that coordinators should promote a positive and supportive sports culture that values student well-being, emphasizes sportsmanship and teamwork, and fosters a sense of belonging among student-athletes. A student-centered approach involves soliciting feedback from student-athletes and reflecting on their experiences to continuously improve sports pro-

grams. Insights from the study indicate that coordinators should actively seek input from student-athletes through surveys, focus groups, and advisory committees, and use this feedback to inform decision-making and program enhancements. A student-centered approach celebrates the achievements and successes of student-athletes, both on and off the field. Insights from the study suggest that coordinators should recognize student-athletes' accomplishments through awards ceremonies, athlete of the month/year recognitions, and public announcements, fostering a culture of recognition and appreciation within sports programs. In summary, a student-centered approach is essential when intensifying sports in the curriculum within educational management. Insights drawn from the findings of the study underscore the importance of providing inclusive opportunities, individualized support, empowerment and ownership, personalized development, focus on well-being, feedback and reflection, and celebrating achievements to create meaningful and impactful sports experiences for student-athletes within schools. By prioritizing the needs and aspirations of student-athletes, educational management can create supportive and enriching sports programs that contribute to the overall development and success of students. A comprehensive study by Cheon et al. (2014) when students have opportunities to participate in sports activities of their choice, they are more likely to be intrinsically motivated and committed to their athletic endeavors. A student-centered approach fosters a sense

of ownership and investment in sports participation, leading to increased enthusiasm and sustained student engagement. Based on the figure above, three themes emerged from the participants' responses: the importance of a holistic approach, resource management strategies, and a student-centered approach. The importance of a holistic approach: Educational management must adopt a holistic approach that considers the interconnectedness of various aspects of student development, including academic, physical, social, and emotional well-being. The study's insights emphasize the significance of recognizing sports as an integral part of the curriculum that contributes to comprehensive student growth and development. A holistic approach ensures that sports programs are aligned with educational goals and promote the overall well-being of students, fostering a positive school culture and enhancing the overall educational experience. Resource management strategies and effective resource management are essential for the successful implementation of sports programs within educational institutions. The study findings highlight the importance of strategic budget allocation, seeking external funding sources, maximizing existing resources, efficient facility management, volunteer recruitment, and advocating for resource needs. Educational management must prioritize resource management strategies that ensure adequate funding, facilities, equipment, and staffing to support sports programs while optimizing resource utilization and addressing budget constraints.

4. Implications and Future Directions

The study "Intensifying Sports in the Curriculum: Perspective of the School Coordinators" delves into the practical implications of the findings and suggests potential future directions for enhancing sports programs within educational settings. This chapter serves to translate the research findings into actionable recommendations for academic management and to identify areas for further exploration and development in the field of sports education.

4.1. Findings—

Fig. 5. Emerging themes on the educational management insights drawn from the study

In summary, the insights drawn from the findings of the study highlight the importance of a holistic approach, resource management strategies, and a student-centered approach in educational management when intensifying sports in the curriculum. By embracing these

themes, educational institutions can effectively integrate sports into the curriculum, promote comprehensive student development, optimize resource utilization, and create meaningful and impactful sports experiences for students.

4.2. Implications—The experiences of school coordinators on intensifying sports in the curriculum led to the emergence of three themes from the responses of the participants which were challenges with resources, balancing academic and athletic priorities, and increased student engagement. As to challenges with resources, school coordinators frequently encounter limitations in funding, which affects their ability to procure necessary resources for sports programs. This includes financial constraints for equipment, facilities, coaching staff, and transportation. Limited resources may result in outdated or insufficient facilities and equipment, impacting the quality of sports programs and student experiences. Coordinators often need to navigate budget constraints by seeking alternative funding sources, negotiating partnerships with local businesses or commu-

nity organizations, or creatively allocating existing resources. By balancing academic and athletic priorities, coordinators face the challenge of balancing academic commitments and athletic pursuits for students. Intensifying sports in the curriculum requires effective time management strategies to ensure students excel academically while participating in sports activities. Providing academic support for student-athletes, such as tutoring, study halls, or flexible scheduling, becomes essential to maintain academic performance alongside sports engagement. Coordinators must collaborate closely with teachers, coaches, and administrators to coordinate schedules, set clear expectations, and prioritize student well-being in both academic and athletic endeavors. Increased student engagement, intensifying sports in the curriculum often leads to higher levels of student engagement and par-

participation in sports activities. By offering a diverse range of sports programs that cater to various interests and abilities, coordinators promote inclusivity and create opportunities for more students to get involved. Coordinators actively promote sports programs, organize events, and incorporate student feedback to enhance student awareness and participation in sports activities, fostering a sense of belonging and school pride among participants. These three themes encapsulate the challenges, priorities, and outcomes that school coordinators navigate when intensifying sports in the curriculum. Despite the challenges with resources and the need to balance academic and athletic priorities, the goal of increasing student engagement remains central to creating meaningful and impactful sports experiences within the school community. Coping mechanisms with the challenges on intensifying sports in the curriculum. Based on the figure above, three themes emerged from the responses of the participants which were advocacy and communication, professional development, and community partnership on coping mechanisms with the challenges on intensifying sports in the curriculum. Indeed, three prominent themes emerged from the responses regarding coping mechanisms with the challenges of intensifying sports in the curriculum. These themes are advocacy and communication, professional development, and community partnerships. Advocacy and communication are foundational in addressing challenges related to intensifying sports in the curriculum. School coordinators advocate for the importance of sports programs within the school and community, effectively communicating the benefits to various stakeholders. Through advocacy and communication efforts, coordinators raise awareness about the challenges they face, such as limited resources or balancing academic and athletic priorities. They articulate the needs of sports programs and advocate for support from school administrators, teachers, parents, and community members. Professional development serves as a coping mechanism by empowering school coordinators with the knowledge, skills, and resources needed to effectively manage challenges related to intensifying sports in the curriculum. By participating in professional development opportunities, coordinators enhance their leadership abilities, stay updated on best practices in sports management, and learn strategies for overcoming obstacles such as budget constraints or staffing challenges. Professional development also fosters networking and collaboration among coordinators, providing a supportive environment for sharing experiences, seeking advice, and finding solutions to common challenges. Community partnerships offer a valuable coping mechanism by providing access to additional resources, expertise, and support from external organizations and stakeholders. Coordinators collaborate with local sports organizations, businesses, and community centers to access facilities, equipment, coaching expertise, and financial support that may not be available within the school. Through community partnerships, coordinators expand the reach and impact of sports programs, engage the broader community in supporting sports initiatives, and create sustainable networks of support that enhance the overall success of sports programs. In summary, advocacy and communication, professional development, and community partnerships are interconnected coping mechanisms that school coordinators utilize to address challenges and effectively manage the process of intensifying sports in the curriculum. By leveraging these strategies, coordinators can overcome obstacles, enhance the quality of sports programs, and create meaningful experiences for student-athletes within their schools. On educational management insights drawn from the study, the emerging themes were importance of holistic approach, resource management strategies, student-centered approach. Importance of holistic approach, educational management

must adopt a holistic approach that considers the interconnectedness of various aspects of student development, including academic, physical, social, and emotional well-being. Insights from the study emphasize the significance of recognizing sports as an integral part of the curriculum that contributes to comprehensive student growth and development. A holistic approach ensures that sports programs are aligned with educational goals and promote the overall well-being of students, fostering a positive school culture and enhancing the overall educational experience. Resource management strategies, effective resource management is essential for the successful implementation of sports programs within educational institutions. The study findings highlight the importance of strategic budget allocation, seeking external funding sources, maximizing existing resources, efficient facility management, volunteer recruitment, and advo-

cating for resource needs. Educational management must prioritize resource management strategies that ensure adequate funding, facilities, equipment, and staffing to support sports programs while optimizing resource utilization and addressing budget constraints. Student-centered approach, a student-centered approach is crucial for designing sports programs that meet the diverse needs and interests of students. Insights from the study underscore the importance of providing inclusive opportunities, individualized support, empowerment, personalized development, focus on well-being, feedback, and recognition of student achievements. Educational management must prioritize the needs and aspirations of student-athletes, involving them in decision-making processes, providing academic and athletic support services, and creating supportive environments that promote their holistic development and success.

4.3. Future Directions—The future directions for policymakers, school administrators, and teachers regarding intensifying sports in the curriculum, as perceived from the perspective of school coordinators encompass various aspects aimed at enhancing sports programs within educational settings. Policymakers can work towards developing supportive policies at the governmental level that recognize the importance of sports in education and allocate resources accordingly. This may include establishing guidelines for integrating sports into the curriculum, funding sports programs, and promoting physical education requirements. Policymakers can incentivize collaboration between educational institutions and community organizations by offering grants, tax incentives, or other forms of support to schools that engage in partnerships to enhance sports programs. School administrators can prioritize resource allocation to support sports programs within their schools. This may involve reallocating funds from other ar-

reas, seeking external funding sources, or implementing cost-effective strategies to maximize resource utilization. Administrators can invest in professional development opportunities for teachers and coordinators involved in sports management. This includes training sessions, workshops, and certifications on sports coaching, program development, and student support services. Administrators can foster community partnerships to enhance sports programs within their schools. This involves collaborating with local sports organizations, businesses, and community centers to access resources, facilities, and expertise to support sports initiatives. Teachers can integrate sports-related content into their curriculum to reinforce learning objectives and promote interdisciplinary connections. This may involve incorporating sports themes into lesson plans, organizing field trips to sports events, or incorporating physical activity breaks into classroom routines. Teachers can encourage student engagement in sports ac-

tivities by providing opportunities for participation, organizing intramural or extracurricular sports teams, and recognizing student achievements in sports through awards and recognition programs. Teachers can collaborate with school coordinators to support sports programs within their schools. This includes assisting with coaching, supervising sports events, and providing academic support to student-athletes to ensure they balance their academic and athletic commitments effectively. Future directions for policymakers, school administrators, and teachers on intensifying sports in the curriculum should focus on strategic resource allocation, professional development, community engagement, integration into the curriculum, promoting student engagement, and collaboration between stakeholders to enhance sports programs within educational settings. These efforts aim to ensure that sports are effectively integrated into the curriculum, promoting the holistic development and well-being of students.

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